

SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURES

Figure S1. Left lateral views of the cloaca and hindgut in control (a) and *Rarabg*^{ΔE10.5} mutant (b) littermates at E10.5, as indicated. CL, lumen of the cloaca; hG and tG, lumen of the hindgut and tailgut, respectively; WD, Wolffian duct. Same magnifications in (a,b).

Figure S2. Left lateral (**a,c**) and ventral (**b,d**) views of the cloaca and arteries in control and *Rarabg*^{ΔE10.5} mutant embryos at E10.5, as indicated. In both mutant and control embryos, the cloaca (CL) starts developing between the roots of umbilical arteries; the latter originate from the ventral wall of the aorta; the umbilical arteries diverge round the anterior portion of the cloaca, come together ventrally and unite to form a single vessel; the principal artery to the hind-limb arises from the lateral side of the ipsilateral umbilical root. AMA, anterior mesenteric artery; DA, midline dorsal aorta; tG, tail gut; rPA and fPA, right and left arteries to the hind-limb buds; r.root and f.root, roots of the right and left umbilical arteries; rUA, fUA, and mUA, right, left and middle umbilical arteries, respectively. The white asterisks indicate the position of mesenchyme that is common to the wall of the cloaca and umbilical roots. Same magnification in (**a-d**).

Figure S3. Left lateral (a,c) and ventral (b,d) views of the urogenital sinus (UGS), hindgut and arteries in control and *Rarabg*^{ΔE10.5} mutant embryos at E13.5, as indicated. (a,b) In the control, the left and the right umbilical arteries have similar calibres; their roots have yielded the common iliac arteries. (c,d) In the mutant, the left umbilical root has regressed; the right root is in a median position and is hyperplastic as it carries the whole umbilical circulation; the principal artery to the right hind-limb bud connects directly to the dorsal aorta; the iliac arteries and posterior mesenteric artery have not formed. AMA, anterior mesenteric artery; CA, celiac artery; DA, midline dorsal aorta; rIA and lIA, right and left common iliac arteries; rPA and fPA, right and left arteries to the hind-limb buds; root, root of the single umbilical artery in the mutant; PMA, posterior

mesenteric artery; rUA and fUA, right and left umbilical arteries. UGS, lumen of the urogenital sinus. Same magnification in **(a-d)**.

Figure S4. External appearance of a control (a-b) and a *Rarabg*^{ΔE9.5} mutant (c-d) littermates at E13.5. (a,c) Left lateral and (b,d) frontal views. The median cleft of the face (black left-right arrow) is a characteristic features of the *Rarabg*^{ΔE9.5} phenotype. White arrowheads point to the generalized subcutaneous oedema.

Figure S5. RAR binding sites at *Hoxa13* and *Wnt5a* loci. University of California at Santa Cruz (UCSC) genome browser (<http://genome.ucsc.edu>) screenshots showing the sequence tag density of the RAR-occupied sites in F9 cells at the *Hoxa13* (upper panel) and *Wnt5a* (lower panel) loci in NCBI37/mm9 assembly, according to Chatagnon et al., 2015. Blue filled boxes and thin lines indicate exons and introns, respectively. Broken arrows indicate the transcription start sites and the gene orientation. RARE point to the RAR-binding regions, as identified according to Chatagnon et al. (2015). The mouse DNA sequence located around the predicted RARE motifs present under the peak are indicated above each locus. Below are alignments of the DNA sequences from the indicated species, corresponding to the RAR-binding region in the mouse genes. The dotted arrows indicate orientations of the core motifs (5'-RGKTCA-3'). Grey boxes highlight the RAR-binding sequences that are

conserved in all 6 species. DR0 and DR5 indicate direct repeats separated by 0 and 5 nucleotides, respectively. Scale bar indicates 1kb.